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THE ORAL AND WRITTEN INTERFACE IN SMS: TECHNOLOGICALLY MEDIATED COMMUNICATION IN KENYA

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1 *Introduction*

The focus of this paper is on the effect of language on literacy in the wake of new technological communication media like the mobile phone and SMS. We show how both oral and written language functioned in the early community followed by the sudden transition into the technological communication age. We then illustrate how the SMS as a type of new technological communication has brought with it a different form of language use, which breaks away from the norm or standard language as we know it and has led to a form of new orthography. We exemplify this by focusing on one SMS practice that we refer to as pronounceable spelling (words written in the way they would be pronounced) and investigate whether this orthography is influenced by the syllabic make-up, and the orthography used to write Swahili.

The data used is in form of SMS messages from university students in Kenya, a country in East Africa with over 42 vernaculars, Swahili as a lingua franca and English as a second language. This group represents the youth in society and it is deemed that their SMS language use is representative of other youth from multilingual backgrounds with English as a second language.

2 *Oral and written language in Kenya*

Oral language has been multifunctional in the Kenyan tradition just like in many other African countries. It was used both in formal contexts like in courts, trade and in informal contexts like in private conversations. Apart from face to face communication, it was also used for long distance communication with the help of a messenger. The only variation in its use was in the level of the formality of the language to suit the occasion. The benefits of oral communication included its spontaneity, speed, affordability and its freedom to be accompanied by gestures and other paralinguistic features.

In 1962, Sigmund Freud described writing simplistically as ‘the voice of an absent person.’ It is notable that some African communities were aware of the value of the written word and possessed established writing systems in the early 19th century, for example the Vai script in Liberia, or the Ge’ez in Ethiopia and Eritrea. However in Kenya, the written language gained a lot of popularity with the introduction of formal education by the British missionaries and the colonial government.

Initially, the written language was mainly used for formal communication. Its main advantages included its ability for preservation and documentation for later retrieval. It was propelled by literacy which came with challenges, for example, the fact that reading and writing went hand in hand and one required the knowledge of both in order to use one. An additional challenge was that the preferred language of literacy was English; therefore writing involved the knowledge of another language. These challenges made writing to be a preserve of the few elite. After Kenya's independence, the postcolonial government continued with the task of enhancing literacy levels in all parts of the country and writing soon came to be associated with intellectualism. It was a sign of status.

Writing became more popularized as more young people enrolled into schools for formal education. It broadened its scope to incorporate informal uses like interpersonal communication for example in letter writing between friends and family. Letter writing was useful in long distance communication. Even illiterate people realized this and would call on their literate counterparts to help write the letter while they dictated the content. Soon the users experienced the disadvantages of letter writing. It was an expensive medium requiring a paper, pen, envelope and postage stamps. Although hand delivery letters could exclude the envelope and postage stamps, they lacked privacy. The postal letters needed the envelope and stamps and had to pass through a slow and unreliable postage system and in many cases they never got to their intended destination.

With this background, it is not surprising that when the mobile phone emerged, it was received wholeheartedly by the masses. It was viewed as a medium that could not only combine both oral and written communication, but could also bridge long distances in a very short time. We will now focus on the SMS that is the written form of communication for the mobile phone users.

3 *SMS / text message*

SMS is an abbreviation of Short Message Service. It is also commonly referred to as text message. It is a service that enables the transmission of typed text messages from one mobile phone to another.

The SMS came to use shortly after the appearance of cell phones. As soon as the mobile phone handsets, network subscriptions and recharging cards became available and affordable in the early 2000s, the SMS immediately became the most widespread communication method. It particularly became very popular among mobile phone users because of its affordability and reliability. For example, the mobile phone networks made it in such a way that an SMS is cheaper than a voice call thus more cost effective, and faster than a letter. In addition, it was very reliable such that if one sends an SMS, it is transmitted and displayed on the screen of the receiver's phone. The receiver is alerted of the incoming SMS by a beep or ring tone from the phone. In case the receiver is not in range or if the phone is switched off, then the SMS will keep pending for a number of days until the phone gets back into the network range or until it is switched on. Some networks allow the sender to be notified when the SMS has been received. In cases of failed transmission perhaps due to a non-existent recipient's number or insufficient credit or airtime on the sender's phone, then the sender is

notified that the SMS transmission failed.

The SMS offers many advantages:

- it is cheaper than the voice call,
- it is less intrusive, i.e. nobody hears you sending the message nor can one decipher what the incoming message is all about,
- it enables direct conveyance of the message without interruption from the recipient,
- it can be saved for future reference unlike the spontaneous spoken word,
- it offers a choice e.g. to reply, forward, or delete them.

The main disadvantages of text messages are that they can be cumbersome to type, are only accessible to literate people, and one has to abide by the limitation which will be described in the next section.

4 *SMS and written language*

According to Bodomo (2009) new communication technologies do not only generate new forms and uses of language, but also new forms of literacy which are associated with the introduction and uses of new technologies. This holds true for SMS communication.

A major element of SMS communication is its limitation of 160 characters per message. Although this limitation has been removed in some networks, its effects are still strong. It has hugely affected the written language with the need for messages to be compacted to fit in this limit while still managing to communicate effectively. One therefore has to think clearly on how to best phrase the message in order to put the point across with the fewest possible number of words so as not to exceed the word limit (Döring 2002; Hård af Segerstad 2002; Ling 2005).

This need has led to creativity in the use of multilingualism and other methods like word shortening, abbreviation, use of numerals, graphemes (see next section), and single pronounceable letters in order to stay within the character limit. This creativity is popular amongst the youth users. Thurlow & McKay (2003) aptly put it that certainly, new communication technologies can empower young people and many do indeed explore and develop imaginative ways of making the technology work best for them.

The creativity makes SMS language to be a kind of independent written register that does not necessarily use the conventions of the written language as we know it. SMS language is used in a very free way just like speech between very close friends.

It has been labeled as Internet slang, webslang, chattisch, netspeak, netlingua, digital English, textese and so on (Thurlow 2007). This has made it liable to strong dismissal by many like Crystal (2001) who wrote off SMS language as simply giving young people something to do. It was followed by Sutherland's (2008) critique that,

As a dialect, text ('textese?') is thin and – compared, say, with Californian personalized license plates – unimaginative. It is bleak, bald, sad shorthand. Drab shrinktalk. In fact linguistically it's all pig's ear and best described as penmanship for illiterates.

The supposition that youth SMS language is a threat to standard writing has come

to evoke a range of projected fears among literate adults and language education practitioners. An eye-opener to this is the report by Australia's ABC radio that Australian educators in Victoria are stirring up a bit of a storm by teaching SMS text messaging as part of a language arts curriculum to high school students (Donovan, 2006). The students practice writing in the short message format that is common in text messaging and putting together their own glossaries of texting abbreviations. They also compare the language and syntax of text messaging with that of formal, written English. It is therefore necessary to carry out more research on this issue in order to be able to come up with an amicable counteraction if indeed this threat is true.

At this juncture, we would like to present the findings of a study on graphemes which is one of the creativity features of SMS that could influence writing in English among learners. The data indicating the graphemes is derived from a data set of a more extensive research investigating the manifestation of language in technologically mediated communication in Kenya. In the current paper, we have used the SMS data that shows the utilisation of graphemes to communicate.

5 *Graphemes*

This study defines the term grapheme as a feature of SMS language in which words are written the way they are pronounced (spoken like writing). This comes from the words 'graphic' (written representation) and phone (speech sound). Grapheme writing in Kenya seems to be closely influenced by Swahili.

As already pointed out, the average Kenyan possesses at least three languages, namely a vernacular, Swahili and English. The vernacular is mainly used locally at the domestic level, while Swahili is the national lingua franca and English is mainly used for formal communication and also amongst the elite. Owing to various reasons like illiteracy, urbanization, intermarriages etc., it is now becoming common for people to possess, a combination of a vernacular and Swahili or Swahili and English. The youth also use a form of slang referred to as Sheng.

Swahili orthography stays very close to pronunciation. Swahili phonology is characterised by a CV syllable structure. It has a five vowel system [a], [e], [i], [ɔ] and [u] represented as *a*, *e*, *i*, *o*, and *u*.

Our data corpus revealed the use of graphemes in English messages where the words were not written with their original spelling but rather in the way that they would be pronounced. In extreme cases, the receiver is forced to pronounce the graphemes loudly in order to understand the intended word and meaning.

This feature seems to be integrated into English messages because of the syllabic nature of the Swahili language and its orthography that enables lexemes to be read and pronounced in the way that they are written.

Below are some examples of the different types of graphemes from the data set. Both the graphemes in the original SMS and their translations are highlighted. The message is followed by a translation into the conventional writing. Note that some messages have used both Swahili and English words. The general English 'translation' is given below the examples.

- (1) *I kof @ ua thot, sniz @ ua smel n cry wen u smyl @ me coz u r 2 much 4 me*
 ‘I cough at your thought, sneeze at your smell, and cry when you smile at me
 because you are too much for me.’

In example (1), besides the pronounceable graphones, the writer has incorporated the symbol <@> for ‘at’ and the use of single pronounceable letters, e.g. <n> for ‘and’, <u> for ‘you’ and <r> for ‘are’. Further, numbers have been used in place of words that share their pronunciation, e.g. <2> for ‘to’ or ‘too’ and <4> for ‘for’.

- (2) *M orait niko ofisi tu. iv oredi gt enuf jobo!!*
 ‘I’m alright and just in the office. I’ve already got enough jobs.’

In example (2), it is notable that ‘al’ in ‘alright’ has been changed into its pronounced form [o] in both ‘alright’ and ‘already’. However, <enuf> takes on a different trend whereby we expect it to be <inaf> but it looks as if the writer in this case decided to keep some of the original letters in the word.

- (3) *Send the rekodz ova pls*
 ‘Send the records over please.’

In example (3), the word records has been written in the way it is pronounced. Interestingly, the word <ova> has been used in place of ‘over’ although it is an English word with its own independent meaning.

- (4) *R u kamin 4 de recoln kesho? Op 2 c u*
 ‘Are you coming for the recollection tomorrow? Hope to see you.’

In example (4), the word coming is spelled with a k. The final g is also deleted since the writer considers them as not pronounced and hence omissible. Similarly, h and e have been left out in hope.

- (5) *jus wishn u a qt dey*
 ‘Just wishing you a quiet day.’

Example (5), has shortened all its words and then written out the word day based on its pronunciation. Also, the message begins with a small letter, a practice that is against the norm language writing.

- (6) *Heey!!! Wats with the silence? a thot we r frenz?? Beat it gal....*
 ‘Hey! What is with the silence? I thought we are friends? Beat it girl.’

In example (6) all the words written out as graphones are shorter than when using conventional spelling. As explained earlier, this helps to fit the message within the character limitation. Notably, the word thought has been spelled as it is pronounced without the use of ugh which is silent in the pronunciation of the word.

Another graphone strategy that we discovered which involves graphones is the substitution of [ai] diphthong with <y> as shown in example (7).

- (7) *stay a little nyl longer.be myt change wit tym*

‘Stay a little while longer. He might change with time.’

Others examples include,

(8) *airtym*
‘airtime’

(9) *lyf*
‘life’

(10) *gyz*
‘guys’

(11) *tryd*
‘tried’

(12) *nyc*
‘nice’

(13) *tym*
‘time’

(14) *gudnyt*
‘goodnight’

(15) *nyz*
‘wise’

In addition to using graphones, people also use letters that represent the standard pronunciation of the letter as a single letter, which we have already seen in <u> for ‘you’ and which is also the mechanism of using <y> for the diphthong [ai] above. Another example is (5).

(16) *thanx*
‘thanks’

In example (16), <x> is used to incorporate the [k] and [s] sounds in the word *thanks*.

(17) *hes faced sm bad xpriens*
‘He’s faced some bad experience.’

In example (17), the contraction ‘he’s’ is written without the hyphen. The word ‘some’ is abbreviated to <sm>. In ‘experience’, the initial part ‘expe’ is written as <xp> using the mechanism of pronouncing as single letter symbols, and the final part the <s> is a graphone again.

6 *Expressing stress and emotional impact by letter repetition*

In an attempt to find some more patterns, we noticed that other mechanisms were used to achieve speech-like qualities for example stress and tone in order to achieve the intended impact similar to oral speech. This is not necessarily a case of writing in a phonetic way but rather in the standard way but contained letter/word repetition to achieve tone and stress. Vowels, consonants and even in some cases words, and punctuation marks are repeated in messages in order to achieve emphasis and verbal impact just like in actual speech. For example in message (16), the word <Heeey> has been used instead of 'hey' to achieve stress.

We begin by giving examples, which use vowel repetition and then move on to consonants.

(18) *niceeeeeeeee videoooooooooooooooo.....*
'nice video'

(19) *had soooooooooo much fun*
'had so much fun'

(20) *wooooooooooooooooo*
'wow!'

(21) *whaaaaaaaaa?????*
'what?'

(22) *byeeee*
'bye'

The following examples display the repetition of consonants in order to achieve stress like in actual speech.

(23) *ffffffyyyy*
'fine'

(24) *it's verrrrrryyyyy good!!!!*
'It's very good!'

The data also revealed other instances of non-standard orthography related to representation of the oral reality which is to capture actions like in examples (25) and (26).

(25) *mmabbbbbbbbbbb*
(kiss)

(26) *hababhababa*
(laughter)

7 Conclusion

The revolution of mobile phone in Kenya (and the rest of Africa) has brought new dimensions to writing and its function in society. The new dimensions are not only due to the space restrictions in SMS messaging, but also to its informal feel and international practices. Owing to this, deviations from the standard orthography are common. The use of graphemes is the deviation that has been discussed in this paper.

The paper has shown how SMS users write messages similar to their verbatim pronunciation and speech production. In fact in view of this, a new orthography is emerging much more based on orality because of the combination of oral and written communication in the mobile phone. In the Kenyan context the impact of this can prove to be huge because for a sizeable number of people, texting is the most common writing experience because it is cheaper than a voice call and can be stored for later access even if the phone is switched off or if the receiver is out of the network reach. Some users find texting as a more private way of communication in addition to the flexibility it offers such that one can choose to store the message for future reference or delete it. All these advantages have popularised the use of SMS and this use in turn leading to the widespread use and acceptance of the orthographic deviations.

8 Recommendations

SMS language is here with us. Its current popularity notwithstanding, it is obvious that users are trying to find daily, practical uses for it. Nadler-Nir (2008) sums this up in his claim that 'SMS is here to stay – and grow – it is a dormant giant which affords us an opportunity to expand our ability to communicate and transact.' We therefore need to accept it and seek for solutions to the complaints that it is invading the standard written language use.

As a first step in averting this threat, SMS needs to be confined to its own communication context. It is then advisable to show its differences from the standard language to the young people affected the most. This can be done right in schools where the major complaints are raised. Students can then be made aware of the differences between standard language and SMS language. Such actions would go a long way in resolving the issue.

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